

Proposal for a new infrastructure evaluation approach: ESFRI and the Social Sciences & Humanities case

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Short Bio

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Research infrastructures (RI) are a cornerstone of contemporary sciences. More and more diffused in the STEM field, they are getting more renowned in the social sciences and humanities. Expensive in terms of time and resource usage, RIs require planned investments and a long-term vision to succeed. A prominent actor in Europe in investing in RIs was, and still is, the European Union – in particular, thanks to the European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI). But, especially in the Social Sciences and Humanities field, it is difficult to understand when the costs overcome the benefits of building a new RI. In this paper, we present a possible alternative to evaluate the success and the benefits of a RI, including the impacts it has not only on the direct scientific community of reference but also the possibility that such RI can have impacts on their local territory of reference – despite many of them being delocalised, digital and/or diffused.

Keywords – ESFRI, research infrastructure, evaluation, European governance, DARIAH, OPERAS, Cost-Benefit Analysis, Social Network Analysis

ESFRI

The European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures (ESFRI) is an attempt made by the European Union, in the context of the European Research Area (ERA), to answer to the lack of state-sponsored research infrastructures (RI) in the continent (ESFRI, 2020). Included in the ERA strategy, ESFRI can be considered a network operating to develop new infrastructures capable of supporting scientists and organisations in any scientific field (ESFRI, 2021).

ESFRI can be deemed an attempt to do *Big Science* (Capershaw and Rader, 1992) in an environment where the costs of research are increasing due to the much more elevated complexity of the issues faced (Cramer & Al., 2020). We can define a Research Infrastructure as a facility, a resource or a service used by the scientific community to pursue its work and research activity (European Union, 2013). This means we can include in the definition of RI many different tools and instruments at the disposition of the scientific community, such as entire laboratories or even databases.

Of their nature of being the link and the environment to foster cooperation and collaboration between experts, RIs are deeply interlinked with the world surrounding them. We can read them as deeply involved in that Triple – or Quadruple – Helix (Ierapetritis, 2019), which involves actors of the political, economic, social and cultural world altogether.

EVALUATING INFRASTRUCTURES

If STEM RIs received attention in the last decades (Cfr. Florio, 2019; Florio et al., 2016; Farago, 2014) due to the amplitude of the studies conducted in such environments and their relevance for the future of science, RIs in the Social Sciences and Humanities (SSH) are a more recent trend (Farago, 2014). The diffusion of new RIs in the SSH is strongly linked with its new-born necessities, such as a significant reliance on empirical data in massive datasets, the challenge of globalisation and the increased dependence on digital and informatics assets (Catalano et al., 2020).

The more the RIs start to grow and diffuse, the more it becomes relevant to how it is possible to evaluate the well-being of an infrastructure. As the massive investment they are, and in a limited resources environment, it becomes necessary for the policymaker to fully understand how the infrastructure will, on the one hand, be sustained in the long-term and if it will impact a significant size of the scientific community. ESFRI is not new to evaluation. Not only as a case study for specialists (Cfr. Zakaria et al., 2021; Franciosi et al., 2012) but also as internally scrutinised by the same European Union. The AEG (Franciosi et al., 2012) is an example of how ESFRI look at itself to improve and better face the challenges ahead of it. A team of experts and evaluators had the task of analysing the different infrastructures – projects and landmarks – considered by ESFRI as possible future infrastructures of the European programme. Using the tools of the in-deep questionnaire, the AEG focused on how each infrastructure faced different challenges – such as how to get new financing, their legal structure and so on.

COST-BENEFIT ANALYSIS

The Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA) (Florio, 2019) proved essential in evaluating the performance of infrastructures, particularly the STEM ones. This methodology allows analysing a RI from both a financial and an economic perspective. If the financial side encompasses all the funding and budget operations, the economic analysis focuses on a broader range of effects and possible impacts an RI can have – i.e., impacting stakeholders outside the original organisation of the RI itself (Florio et al., 2016).

CBA introduced in the analysis of an infrastructure what we can label as local effects (Battistoni et al., 2016). The local effects can be direct or indirect consequences a RI can have on a territory – both urban and rural – such as creating new jobs or economic opportunities for a territory or increasing the social or cultural capital around the RI (Battistoni et al., 2016).

ANALYSING LOCAL EFFECTS

This combination of local effects is challenging to evaluate. At the same time, they can be the relevant outcomes of RIs belonging to SSH. Focusing on two infrastructures of ESFRI, DARIAH and OPERAS, we aim to explore the possibility that such infrastructures – even if delocalised – could directly sustain the institutions joining them – i.e., supporting their capacity to produce knowledge and attire new talents –, but at the same time, their effects could expand to stakeholders and actors (political, social, and economic ones) who interact with such institutions.

We can summarise the possible effects our RIs can have in four elements:

- (i) Increase the calculus capacity of the single institutions entering the RI.
- (ii) Refine the local academics' and experts' capacities, allowing them to connect with a broader

audience and access more connections on non-local scales.

(iii) RIs should be able to connect the scientific community, improving the capacity of cooperation between different ones.

(iv) The RIs could have a spillover effect over the bottom-up network construction capacity of the local stakeholders and actors, who find themselves inside a more extensive network.

Some of these outcomes are directly linked with the capacity of the infrastructure itself to sustain the institutions. Some others are, instead, more intertwined with the capacity of the infrastructure to foster a new form of cooperation between different stakeholders belonging to the local realities.

We aim to use two different approaches to perform this attempt to evaluate our two infrastructures. Using the Social Network Analysis (SNA), we aim to understand and describe the functioning of the network built around each one of our case studies (Cfr. Giancola and Colarusso, 2020; Crossley et al., 2015). Using both qualitative in-deep interviews with the coordinators of each institution involved and questionnaires, we want to rebuild the network and the stakeholders that could be involved in OPERAS and DARIAH.

Using the SNA, we should be able to reconstruct every single actor and stakeholder position in the network. In the second phase of our analysis, we aim to understand the impact using the CBA itself (Florio, 2019) or adapting other impact evaluation techniques based on our data availability (Cfr. Reale et al., 2017).

CONCLUSION

What we expect from the upcoming analyses we aim to perform in the following years is to better understand how infrastructures operating in the SSH field could impact the institutions joining them and the territories where such institutions are located. Considering both DARIAH and OPERAS are digitalised and delocalised, this does not mean the institutions are not spatial entities strongly connected to stakeholders and actors, which are, in our hypothesis, influenced by the RIs. We aim to assess how these effects can be analysed not only in the form of a direct impact – on the institution and the stakeholder – but as a whole-network effect.

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